

Investigation of Chlorine Cross Sections in Molten Chloride Fast Reactors Using Peacock

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803857

ABSTRACT

Molten Chloride Fast Reactors (MCFRs) have been of interest for several years now and they offer many innovations compared to traditional nuclear power reactors. For example, MCFRs avoid risk associated with fuel meltdown as the fuel is designed to be a liquid and the fast neutron spectrum allows diverse fuel cycles, including the possibility of breeding fissile material. However, the uncertainty in the fundamental nuclear data of chlorine has proven to be a challenge while designing these reactors. Specifically, the neutron cross sections of ³⁵Cl have challenged reactor designers. Recently, TerraPower and Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) have collaborated to improve the evaluation of the ³⁵Cl cross sections. In this work, Peacock, the new continuous-energy Monte Carlo code developed by Studsvik Scandpower, Inc. (SSP) is used with the updated ³⁵Cl nuclear data to investigate its impact on a representative MCFR design. It is shown that the new nuclear data has a significant impact on the reactivity in a representative MCFR with natural (unenriched) chlorine.

Keywords: Molten Chloride Fast Reactor, Peacock, TerraPower, ENDF/B

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of a Molten Chloride Fast Reactor (MCFR) is an attractive one. It avoids several safety design considerations such as meltdown by using a liquid fuel. The fuel composition is a homogeneous mixture which allows for simplified modeling. Finally, the fast neutron spectrum allows a variety of fuel cycle designs, including the possibility of breeding fissile material.

However, uncertainty in the fundamental nuclear data in chlorine has proved to be a challenge when designing these reactors. There are two naturally occurring isotopes of chlorine: ³⁵Cl and ³⁷Cl, with natural abundances of 76 % and 24 % respectively [1]. Of these two, it is known that ³⁵Cl is a significant parasitic neutron absorber. It is common for conceptual MCFR designs to enrich chlorine to remove ³⁵Cl. Recent evaluations of ³⁵Cl neutron cross sections have resulted in modifications of the neutron cross section by a few orders of magnitude, particularly in the high-energy region relevant to MCFRs [2].

The relatively large uncertainty has led to difficulty in designing MCFRs. First, it can be difficult to quantify the necessary critical mass and/or uranium enrichment if the amount of parasitic absorption in ³⁵Cl is unknown. Second, designers must be able to consider the economic trade-offs between chlorine enrichment and the neutron economy in the fission process.

Uncertainty in the ³⁵Cl cross sections and interest driven by TerraPower led to recent collaboration with Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) and re-evaluation of the underlying nuclear data [2, 3]. Specifically, the (*n, p*) reaction channel (MT103) was re-evaluated in the energy range of 300 keV to 12 MeV [4]. Other work has compared the newer ³⁵Cl evaluations with older data from ENDF/B-VII.0, ENDF/B-VII.1, and ENDF/B-VIII.0 [2, 3]. This work revisits this new evaluation of nuclear data after the ENDF/B-VIII.1 release in August 2024 [5].

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While the experience and nuclear data expertise of Studsvik Scandpower, Inc. (SSP) has traditionally focused on modeling and simulation of Light Water Reactors (LWRs), Peacock has led to further usage and exploration of nuclear data [6, 7]. Peacock is a new continuous-energy Monte Carlo code developed by SSP for modeling in reactor physics applications [8, 9]. While previous neutron transport methods at SSP relied on pre-processed, multi-group nuclear data, Peacock allows engineers to investigate new evaluations of nuclear data directly and how it may impact reactor performance. Peacock is developed within the SSP Nuclear Quality Assurance-1 (NQA-1) program and will be delivered with 10 CFR Part 21 error reporting so engineers can move directly from investigating new nuclear data evaluations to using that nuclear data in downstream analyses for real reactor designs.

In this work, Peacock is used to model a representative MCFR. The MCFR design is considered with and without enriched chlorine. Then, the MCFR model is used to investigate the reactivity impact of the new ^{35}Cl evaluation. Finally, the new impact of the ^{35}Cl evaluation is investigated for its impact on multi-group cross section data.

2. PEACOCK NUCLEAR DATA

In Peacock, a proprietary Grid Unionization and Thinning (GUT) methodology is used to perform continuous energy neutron transport on a unionized energy grid. The GUT methodology in Peacock is based on earlier work by Leppänen with additional heuristic rules designed for efficient modeling of fission-driven reactor systems [10]. The continuous-energy nuclear data in Peacock is unionized at the library-level which requires a moderate amount of pre-processing. The decision to unionize the energy grid at the time of library generation was made to permit simplified temperature interpolation and to be able to quantify the memory required for depletion calculations at the time of library-generation rather than at runtime.

For this work, Peacock continuous-energy libraries were generated based on ENDF/B-VII.1 (E7R1) and ENDF/B-VIII.1 (E8R1) data [11, 5]. As the new ^{35}Cl evaluation data are expected to be included in the next release of the ENDF/B data, a third nuclear data library was created with the E8R1 data and only the ^{35}Cl data modified. This new nuclear data library was termed ENDF/B-IX.0 β 0 (E9R0 β 0) for the purpose of this work.

3. MODEL DESCRIPTION

A representative MCFR model provided by TerraPower is used in this work [12]. Specifically, the “demonstration” model (MCFR-D) is used here. Although a typical MCFR would have flowing fuel (and moving delayed neutron precursors), the model used in this work assumes that the fuel salt is stationary.

This MCFR model is a series of three nested cylinders of fuel salt, reflector cladding, and reflector. The geometry of this MCFR model is shown in Figure 1.

The original model specification provides basic material definitions. For the purposes of this work, all materials will be assumed to be at 900 K and no thermal expansion modeling will be applied. In the interest of reproducibility, the number densities used in this work are given here explicitly. The number densities of the MgO in the reflector are given in Table I. The number densities of the Inconel-625 reflector cladding are given in Table II based on a representative definition of the alloy [13].

The number densities of the fuel salt composition are given in Table III. The original model specification provides the mass density of the fuel salt as a function of temperature. At the temperature used in this work, the fuel salt is modeled at a density of 3.25 g/cm^3 . The fuel salt is composed of 33.3% UCl_3 and 66.7% NaCl by volume. The uranium in the fuel salt is enriched to 19.75% ^{235}U by mass.

Figure 1. MCFR-D Geometry.

Table I. Reflector Number Densities.

Element	Number Density [$\frac{\text{atom}}{\text{b cm}}$]
Mg	5.378 93E-2
O	5.378 93E-2

Table II. Reflector Clad Number Densities.

Element	Number Density [$\frac{\text{atom}}{\text{b cm}}$]
Ni	5.369 30E-2
Cr	2.066 79E-2
Mo	4.688 42E-3
Nb	1.936 81E-3
Fe	1.790 09E-3
C	2.080 82E-4
Si	3.559 46E-4
Al	3.705 03E-4
Ti	2.088 44E-4
Mn	1.819 64E-4
S	1.558 70E-6

Table III. Fuel Salt Number Densities.

Element	Enriched Cl Density [$\frac{\text{atom}}{\text{b cm}}$]	Natural Cl Density [$\frac{\text{atom}}{\text{b cm}}$]
^{235}U	8.338 16E-4	8.473 32E-4
^{238}U	3.345 24E-3	3.399 47E-3
^{35}Cl	2.208 92E-4	1.609 65E-2
^{37}Cl	2.068 69E-2	5.150 22E-3
Na	8.370 66E-3	8.506 36E-3

 Figure 2. ^{35}Cl Cross Sections.

In the original model description published by TerraPower, the chlorine in the fuel salt is assumed to be enriched to 99% ^{37}Cl by mass. While it is known that ^{35}Cl introduces parasitic neutron absorption that designers may desire to avoid, this work seeks to investigate the effect of new ^{35}Cl cross section evaluations. Therefore, number densities are provided in Table III for compositions with both highly-enriched and natural chlorine (74.7% ^{35}Cl by mass).

4. DISCUSSION OF CHLORINE CROSS SECTIONS

The investigation of the new ^{35}Cl cross sections begins by examining the continuous energy cross sections. The ^{35}Cl absorption cross section, $\sigma_a(E)$, is shown in Figure 2a. The new evaluation focused on the high-energy (n, p) reaction (MT103), shown in Figure 2b [2]. It is worth noting that the (n, p) reaction in ^{35}Cl has no energy threshold, meaning that the reaction is energetically possible for a neutron with zero kinetic energy.

The primary purposes of the re-evaluation were to incorporate new measurements from LANSCE that diverged significantly from the previous evaluation [3, 4] and to resolve "the discontinuity in (n, p) at 1.2 MeV between the previous resonance and statistical analyses."¹ The new evaluation incorporated

¹K. Hanselman, Summary description of LANL-TP reevaluation from the preliminary evaluated data file; personal communication.

Figure 3. Fission Reaction Rate.

Table IV. Effective Multiplication Factor for Different ENDF/B Libraries.

Library	Enriched Chlorine		Natural Chlorine	
	k_{eff}	St. Dev. [pcm]	k_{eff}	St. Dev. [pcm]
ENDF/B-VII.1	1.135 559	4.8	0.995 607	4.2
ENDF/B-VIII.1	1.135 309	4.9	0.997 502	4.2
ENDF/B-IX.0 β 0	1.135 352	5.4	1.002 990	4.4

fitted data from the LANSCE measurements, extending these data as a background cross section to 140 keV and adding the evaluated resonance cross sections in the overlapping energy region.¹ The resulting (n, p) cross section was slightly reduced above 1.2 MeV and increased by several orders of magnitude between 140 keV and 1.2 MeV, effectively smoothing the transition between the resonance and statistical evaluation regions.

While the changes in the (n, p) cross section evaluation appear to be small in magnitude relative to those in the thermal range, they are significant in the fast energy range, where cross sections are orders of magnitude smaller (e.g., the ^{235}U fast fission cross section is on the order of 1 barn). As chloride salt reactors tend to be fast spectrum systems and contain large quantities of chlorine, this seemingly small change in absolute cross section is expected to have a large impact on reactivity.

5. RESULTS

The MCFR-D model described in Section 3 was modeled using Peacock. For all cases in this work, 50 inactive cycles and 100 active cycles were used with one-million particles per cycle. Six separate cases were evaluated: the three different cross section libraries of interest, each with enriched and natural chlorine. A representative visualization of the fission reaction rate distribution computed with Peacock is shown in Figure 3.

5.1. Effect on Reactivity

The effective multiplication factor, k_{eff} , results from the Peacock calculations are shown in Table IV. With highly-enriched chlorine (99% ^{37}Cl by mass), the cross section libraries all yield similar results. All values of k_{eff} computed with enriched chlorine were within a spread of 25 pcm.

Table IV also shows that the E7R1 and E8R1 results with natural chlorine (74.7% ^{35}Cl by mass) are relatively similar. This is expected due to the similarity of the underlying continuous-energy cross section data previously shown in Figure 2. Table IV shows that the E9R0 β 0 cross section evaluation has a very significant effect on the reactivity of this model. The spread of k_{eff} between these nuclear data libraries for the MCFR-D model with natural chlorine is approximately 738 pcm. The magnitude of this reactivity effect is comparable to other results reported previously [3].

While Figure 2b may have suggested that all of the evaluations were comparable, the reactivity results show that these small differences are significant for MCFR designs. It is important to remember that in the fast neutron spectrum, almost all cross sections are small in magnitude so small absolute changes are still large relative changes in cross section.

5.2. Effect on Multi-Group Cross Sections

The multi-group reaction rate tallies in Peacock can be used to investigate the neutron flux spectra and the underlying macroscopic cross sections in this MCFR model. For the purposes of visualization, the neutron flux and associated reaction rates were tallied in the fuel salt with a 200-group equal-logarithmic width energy binning. The results in Table IV demonstrated that the new ^{35}Cl evaluation in the E9R0 β 0 library does not significantly affect the MCFR model with highly-enriched chlorine. Therefore, the results in this section will only consider the MCFR model with natural chlorine.

The neutron flux spectra computed with Peacock is shown in Figure 4a. The tallied neutron flux spectra make it clear that this reactor has a very “hard” (i.e., high-energy) neutron spectrum as almost all of the neutron flux is tallied above the 1 keV sodium resonance. Additionally, Figure 4a shows that the underlying nuclear data library does not significantly affect the computed neutron spectrum.

Tallies in Peacock can be used to compute multi-group cross sections for use in a subsequent multi-group neutron transport or neutron diffusion calculation. Cross sections can be computed in this fashion by tallying the neutron flux spectrum (as in Figure 4a) and the multi-group reaction rate and then dividing the reaction rate by the neutron flux. The absorption reaction rate computed by Peacock in the fuel salt in the MCFR model is shown in Figure 4b and the resulting effective macroscopic cross section is shown in Figure 4c. The definition of the absorption cross section in Peacock is the sum of the (n, p) reaction channel, fission, and all other reactions that do not result in subsequent neutron emission.

Figure 4c shows the significant change in the macroscopic absorption cross section in the fuel salt with the new ^{35}Cl evaluation in the E9R0 β 0 library. The apparent cross section discontinuity from Figure 2b at 1.2 MeV can be seen in the E7R1 and E8R1 results in Figure 4c. The cross section in the E9R0 β 0 results appears to change more smoothly in this high-energy region.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Peacock, the new continuous-energy Monte Carlo code developed by SSP, was used to investigate new evaluations of the ^{35}Cl cross sections in MCFRs. Some proposed MCFR designs intend to use highly-enriched chlorine to mitigate the parasitic absorption of neutrons in ^{35}Cl . However, it is important to accurately quantify the neutron absorption in ^{35}Cl in order to compare the economic choice of chlorine enrichment versus neutron absorption.

This work showed that the new evaluation of the (n, p) reaction channel in ^{35}Cl performed by TerraPower and LANL has a significant impact on reactivity and in the absorption cross section in a representative MCFR. The new ^{35}Cl cross sections resulted in a reactivity increase of approximately 738 pcm in a representative MCFR. In these fast-spectrum reactors, small absolute changes in cross sections can result in large relative changes as all cross sections are relatively small.

Figure 4. Tallied Results with Different ENDF/B Libraries.

The results of modeling a representative MCFR in this work with different nuclear data libraries do not necessarily provide insight into which cross section evaluation is more physically accurate. However, the continuous-energy neutron physics and the generality of Peacock now allow engineers at SSP to investigate the effects of new nuclear data evaluations and how they may affect new reactor designs. Peacock is well-positioned to provide insight into new advanced reactor designs and generate multi-group nuclear data that can be used in later advanced reactor design calculations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge Matt Wargon, Tommy Cisneros, and Bobbi Riedel from TerraPower for sharing the nuclear data files with the updated ^{35}Cl evaluation.

The authors would also like to acknowledge the Cross Section Evaluation Working Group (CSEWG) for facilitating easy access to new nuclear data evaluations.

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